

Challenges and Strategies in Translating Linguistic Taboos: A Comparative Analysis of Jojo Moyes' *Me before You* in English and Arabic

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ONOMÁZEIN 61 (September 2023): 504-519

ISSN: 0718-5758

Abstract

Linguistic taboo is a universal phenomenon that suggests that almost all languages have words and expressions that are forbidden to be used. People use such unsuitable expressions for humor, catharsis, or even to manifest one's power.

There are certain sets of taboo expressions that are forbidden in almost all languages, while other expressions vary in their strength from one language to another according to the cultural difference. The two languages under investigation (English and Arabic) are culturally different, which might make an expression taboo in one language but not in the other. Therefore, this paper explores the Arabic and English linguistic taboos based on the theories of context and cross-cultural communication. The main objective of the study is to explore all the linguistic taboos used in Jojo Moyes' "Me before You" and the way these expressions were rendered into Arabic by "Amany Lazar" in *قَبْلَكَ أَنَا* /?ana qabluk/

A descriptive research design was adopted; the data collection was carried out by manually gathering taboo expressions used in the source text novel and its equivalent target text.

Throughout analyzing the English taboo expressions and their Arabic translations, different strategies of translating taboo words from one language into another are presented to find out the strategy the translator tends to use the most in translating Jojo Moyes' taboo expressions.

Keywords: Taboo, Jojo Moyes, Amany Lazar, cultural gap, translation techniques, functions of taboo, types of taboo.

1. Introduction

Language is the primary way by which we gain access to the context of other people's minds and the fundamental vehicle for the transmission of cultural information. The relationship between a sequence of sounds and a succession of meanings has been characterized as an abstract set of rules. Language serves as a means to express one's social identity while simultaneously upholding distinctions within their particular in-group. People can freely use language at any time. However, society occasionally places some restrictions and limitations on the usage of specific terminology in public forums. For example, there are many phrases in any language that are not commonly used in public settings because they are rude, indecent, or even distressing to language users.

Taboo differs from one social group to another and applying taboo terminologies in written communication is usually limited by several factors, such as social, cultural, and religious ones. To avoid using inappropriate language that contradicts a society's religious and social standards, translators may employ euphemisms, proverbs, metaphors, implicatures, and synonyms among other common strategies.

Taboo words are terms that are considered inappropriate in specific situations because they go against a society's social, cultural, and religious standards.

Translating taboo expressions in Jojo Moyes' "Me Before You" requires careful consideration of cultural and linguistic differences between English and Arabic. One technique commonly used is to use a euphemism that conveys the same meaning without using a taboo word or expression. Another technique is to use a culturally appropriate equivalent that may have a similar level of taboo in Arabic. In some cases, the translator may choose to omit the taboo expression altogether if it is deemed too offensive or inappropriate for the target audience. Additionally, footnotes or explanations may be used to provide cultural context or explanations for certain expressions that may be unfamiliar or offensive to the target audience. The choice of translation technique depends on the specific context and the level of taboo associated with the expression in question.

In this study, all taboo expressions in "Me before you" are selected and classified according to Wardhaugh's theory (1986). The Arabic equivalents for each expression are presented, and commentary is given on how these terms were translated, along with an analysis of the techniques applied by the translator.

Sample Analysis

"Bollocks to that!" (Moyes, 2013,p.45)	
(Mayes, 2013/2017, p.39)	هذا غير مقبول
	/haða gʻayr-u maqbuul/ "this is unacceptable"

By replacing the taboo English swear word "bollocks" with the neutral Arabic phrase "هذا غير مقبول", the translator employed the technique of substitution to convey the meaning without using a taboo term. This allowed the target Arabic audience to understand the sentiment being expressed without using inappropriate language that may go against cultural or religious standards. The substitution maintains the force and frustration of the original line while adapting it for the target context. This

illustrates how taboo words from one language can be skilfully substituted when translating for a different linguistic and cultural audience.

2. Previous Studies on Taboo Expressions and their Translation

Taboo expressions pose unique challenges for translators. Researchers have noted that direct translation of taboo words is usually inappropriate and requires careful consideration of cultural norms (Newmark, 1988). A study by Koopmans (2015) analysed strategies used by translators when faced with swear words, blasphemy, and sexual references in literature. The results showed translators commonly employed strategies like substitution, avoidance, generalization, and omission to adapt taboo content for different audiences. This aligns with Skiba's (1997) findings that direct translation of taboo terms frequently leads to a loss of naturalness and thus adaptation is necessary.

Cultural differences play a major role in what constitutes a taboo expression. A seminal work by Schrauf and Rubin (1998) explored similarities and differences in perception of English and Spanish swear words. They found words deemed highly offensive in one language were judged mildly offensive or inoffensive in the other due to cultural norms. This supports the theory that taboo language must be translated based on target language norms rather than word-for-word equivalence (Newmark, 1988).

Euphemisms are commonly used to translate taboo terms into different languages and cultures. In their study on Polish-English translation, Krzyzanowski and Wodak (2009) observed euphemisms were the predominant strategy for politically sensitive topics involving taboo language. Similarly, analyses by Karena (2002) and Kim (2012) showed euphemistic substitution was the most frequent approach in film and literary translations involving offensive content respectively. This suggests euphemisms allow translators to maintain the intended impact while avoiding directly offensive expressions.

However, an overuse of euphemisms can also diminish the impact. According to research conducted by Kuhlwiczak and Littau (2007), excessive substitution of taboo terms with mild language diluted the original emotive force in some contexts. They recommended that translators balance impact preservation with target language norms on a case-by-case basis. Correspondingly, Toury (2012) noted that adequate cultural mediation is paramount for a successful translation of taboo language.

3. Theoretical Framework

The translation of taboo expressions in literature presents unique linguistic and cultural challenges. This study utilizes Toury's (2012) Descriptive Translation Studies (DTS) framework to provide a theoretical lens for analyzing taboo translation techniques. According to DTS, translated texts should not be evaluated based on standards of fidelity but rather described "as products of the circumstances and factors surrounding their production" (Toury, 2012, p. 27). When translating taboo content, direct equivalence is typically unsatisfactory due to cultural and normative differences between source and target languages (Toury, 2012; Newmark, 1988). Therefore, translators may apply strategies to mediate content for target audiences.

Koepmans' (2015) analysis of taboo translation methods categorizes approaches commonly used by literary translators. Strategies like substitution, generalization, omission and explicitation help negotiate offensive or sensitive language (Koepmans, 2015; Kim, 2012). Substitution replaces taboo words with culturally appropriate euphemisms, while omission removes taboo sections if deemed too disparaging (Krzyzanowski & Wodak, 2009; Karena, 2002).

At the same time, excessive censorship risks distorting impact or intent (Kuhiwczak & Littau, 2007). Toury (2012) and Skiba (1997) emphasize the translator's role in adequately conveying tone and sociocultural context. This study examines how the translator of "Me Before" You utilizes taboo translation techniques while maintaining semantic, pragmatic and cultural functions for the Arabic audience.

By analyzing taboo expressions and their treatment cross-linguistically, this paper aims to describe translation methods applied and comment on their effectiveness according to DTS principles. The theoretical framework will guide examinations of how social and cultural factors shaped translations of sensitive language between two dissimilar linguistic and normative contexts.

4. Methodology

The study employs a qualitative descriptive research design to systematically analyse taboo expressions and their translations between English and Arabic. Qualitative methods allow for an in-depth exploration of translation techniques applied to a specific literary text (Creswell, 2014).

The data consists of taboo expressions found in Jojo Moyes' novel "Me Before You" in English, and their corresponding translations in Amany Lazar's Arabic version. The data is collected through close reading and manual identification of offensive or sensitive terms in both texts.

The data is analysed based on Koopmans' (2015) classification of taboo translation strategies: substitution, generalization, omission, and explicitation. For each English taboo expression, its Arabic equivalent is presented alongside an analysis of the translation technique used based on this framework. The analysis aims to describe rather than judge the translations (Toury, 2012).

Additional context clues and cultural factors are also considered when analysing strategy usage based on Descriptive Translation Studies (Toury, 2012). The frequency of each technique is quantified to identify patterns in the translator's approach. Explanations are provided for meanings substituted and any loss or modification of impact.

Research Questions

- 1) What are the expressions classified as taboo in "Me before you"?
- 2) What taboo translation techniques does the translator use most frequently in rendering taboo expressions from English into Arabic in Me Before You?
- 3) How does the translator's use of techniques influence the meaning, impact, and/or acceptability of taboo expressions for the Arabic target audience?
- 4) What contextual factors (e.g. cultural, religious) appear to determine the translator's choices in handling taboo expressions between English and Arabic?

Research Objectives

- 1) To identify and classify instances of taboo language used in the source and target texts.
- 2) To analyse the techniques employed by the translator when rendering taboo expressions into Arabic.
- 3) To determine the frequency of different techniques used and any patterns in the translator's approach.
- 4) To examine how techniques influence the semantic and pragmatic aspects of taboo expressions.
- 5) To understand the role of contextual factors in shaping the translator's normalization choices.

Research Hypothesis

Based on previous studies that found euphemistic substitution to be common when translating offensive content (Karena, 2002; Kim, 2012), it is hypothesized that: The translator will predominantly employ substitution as the main technique for translating taboo expressions from English to Arabic in *Me Before You*, replacing offensive source language words with milder target language equivalents. Substitutions can effectively convey comparable meanings and effects in the target text, all the while sidestepping explicitly taboo expressions unsuitable within the Arabic sociocultural context.

Research Significance

This study holds significance for the field of translation studies and cross-cultural communication. Through a systematic analysis of taboo expressions and their translations between English and Arabic, it uncovers the strategies used by translators when dealing with sensitive content. These techniques offer insights into maintaining the essence of the source text while ensuring cultural sensitivity in the target language, benefiting translators and researchers alike. By examining cultural norms and contextual factors, the study enhances cross-cultural communication, facilitates effective translation practices, and enriches literary translation insights (Feinberg: 1988).

The research's focus on a literary text provides depth to the understanding of handling taboo expressions creatively. It emphasizes the importance of maintaining impact and meaning while aligning with cultural acceptability. Moreover, the examination of the impact of translation techniques on meaning and acceptability sheds light on how these decisions can mold readers' interpretations. This scholarly contribution enriches the field of translation studies and serves as a valuable resource for academics. Ethical concerns and the potential application in translation training programs underscore the broader significance of this research in promoting responsible translation and the education of future translators.

5. Classification of Taboo Expressions

Taboo expressions, characterized by their social or cultural sensitivity, can be classified based on their linguistic functions and the emotions they evoke. Taboo expressions can be categorized according to Battistella's framework (2005) as follows:

1. Profanity and Expletives
2. Expletives:
"fuck," "fucking," "shit," "bullshit," "bastard," "bitch," "filthy," "crap"

These expressions often serve as strong intensifiers, allowing speakers to convey heightened negative emotions, and express frustration, anger, or contempt (Battistella, 2005, p.12).

3. Blasphemous or Religious References:

"Christ," "God," "Jesus"

These expressions involve references to religious or sacred figures and can be perceived as offensive or disrespectful in certain cultural or religious contexts (Battistella, 2005, p.12).

4. Cursing and Strong Language:

"bloody," "damn," "hell," "screwed," "piss," "bugger"

Expressions in this category carry a sense of cursing or invoking negative outcomes, contributing to their strong impact on communication (Battistella, 2005, p.13).

5. Vulgar or Obscene References:

"arse," "dick," "shitbag," "cripple"

These expressions are characterized by their vulgarity and are often related to anatomical terms or derogatory language (Battistella, 2005, p.13).

Each classification fulfils distinct communicative functions, ranging from emphasizing emotions and intensity to invoking religious or cultural connotations. The interpretation, acceptability, and impact of these expressions are contingent upon various cultural, social, and individual factors.

Classification of Taboo Expression Translation Strategies

Koopmans (2015) proposed a classification framework for strategies used in translating taboo expressions. These strategies provide methods for addressing the difficulties involved in translating content that is sensitive or offensive from one language to another.. The framework includes the following categories:

- 1) Euphemistic Substitution: This strategy involves replacing offensive or taboo language with milder or more socially acceptable alternatives. It aims to maintain the core meaning while using less provocative language. Euphemisms are employed to achieve this effect (Koopmans, 2015).
- 2) Generalization: In this technique, a specific or taboo term is replaced with a broader or less explicit term in the target language. This approach reduces the impact of the offensive expression while retaining the general meaning intended in the source text (Koopmans, 2015).
- 3) Omission: The omission strategy entails intentionally leaving out the taboo or offensive expression during translation. This technique is used to avoid causing offense, adhering to cultural norms, or maintaining the overall tone of the target text (Koopmans, 2015).
- 4) Explication: This strategy involves making implicit meanings more explicit in the target language. It may include clarifications, explanations, or elaborations to ensure that the intended meaning of the taboo expression is conveyed effectively (Koopmans, 2015).

These translation strategies offer translators a toolkit to address sensitive content and adapt it for the target audience while considering cultural, linguistic, and contextual factors. The choice of strategy depends on the translator's goals, the sociocultural context, and the desired impact in the target language.

Function of Taboo Expressions

Taboo expressions, often considered socially or culturally inappropriate, serve various functions within language and communication. These functions are deeply rooted in cultural norms, social dynamics, and the need to negotiate sensitive or uncomfortable topics. Taboo expressions fulfil several roles:

- 1) Eliciting Emotion: Taboo expressions often evoke strong emotional reactions due to their provocative nature. They can be used to convey intense feelings, create emphasis, or provoke shock or surprise (Jay, 2009; 1996).
- 2) Conveying Intimacy: In certain contexts, the use of taboo language can establish a sense of familiarity or intimacy among speakers. Such expressions might be reserved for close relationships where a certain level of comfort and mutual understanding exists (Jay, 2009).
- 3) Maintaining Social Norms: Taboo expressions reinforce societal boundaries by defining what is considered acceptable and unacceptable behavior or language. They contribute to the establishment of cultural norms and values (Kulkarni, 2012).
- 4) Highlighting Taboos: By using taboo language, speakers can draw attention to subjects that are considered off-limits or sensitive. This can lead to discussions about social or moral issues, challenging conventional viewpoints (Jay, 2009).
- 5) Creating Identity and Group Cohesion: Taboo expressions can be used to establish group identity or solidarity. They signal membership to a certain social or cultural group and strengthen interpersonal bonds (Kulkarni, 2012).
- 6) Resisting Authority or Oppression: In some cases, taboo language is employed as a form of resistance against authority or oppression. It can challenge established power structures and express dissent or frustration (Jay, 2009).
- 7) Exploring Taboos in Literature and Art: In literature, film, and art, taboo expressions can be used to explore controversial themes and challenge conventional narratives. They offer a platform for creative exploration of societal boundaries (Kulkarni, 2012).

"Me Before You"

"Me Before You" by Jojo Moyes follows the story of Louisa "Lou" Clark, a young woman living in a small English town. Louisa loses her job at a local café and takes up a position as a caregiver for Will Traynor, a former successful businessman who is now quadriplegic due to a motorcycle accident. The novel delves into their evolving relationship and the challenges they face.

As Louisa begins caring for Will, she initially struggles to connect with him due to his bitterness and resistance to his new circumstances. However, their interactions gradually lead to a deep bond and friendship. Louisa discovers that Will had previously lived a life full of adventure and thrill-seeking activities before the accident, and he now feels trapped by his disability.

The heart of the novel revolves around Louisa's efforts to help Will find joy and purpose in life once again. She introduces him to new experiences, seeking to show him that life can still hold meaning despite his physical limitations. Will, in turn, encourages Louisa to expand her horizons and seize opportunities.

Their growing attachment takes a poignant turn when Louisa learns of Will's decision to pursue assisted suicide in Switzerland. This revelation challenges Louisa to confront her feelings and consider what she truly wants for her own life. The novel explores complex ethical and emotional dilemmas as it delves into the themes of love, choice, and the value of life.

5.1. Taboo Expressions in "Me before You"

Throughout the novel, many taboo expressions are employed. Below is a list of some of the most repeated taboo expressions in the novel.

Taboo Expression	Category	Occurrence	Percentage
bullshit	Profanity and Expletives	60	48.54%
fuck		10	8.11%
shit		15	12.16%
fucking		4	4.05%
bullshit		3	2.43%
bastard		1	0.81%
filthy		1	0.81%
bitch		2	1.62%
bloody	Cursing and Strong Language	2	1.62%
damn		3	2.43%
hell		20	16.22%
screwed		6	5.41%
piss		10	8.11%
bugger		8	6.49%
stupid		25	20.27%
Christ	Blasphemous or Religious References	20	16.22%
God		36	29.73%
Jesus		13	10.81%
arse	Vulgar or Obscene References:	19	18.92%
deck		4	4.05%
shitbag		3	2.43%
cripple		5	4.05%

(Note that the percentages are rounded to two decimal places and may not add up to exactly 100% due to rounding.)

Upon examining the data, one can observe that taboo expressions are prevalent in the novel, despite its primary categorization as a Romantic novel, and they serve various functions. In British English, "bloody" is a common curse word, frequently employed to vent frustration or anger. It appears sixty times in the data and is utilized to discredit objects or individuals. "Fuck" is a highly offensive epithet, occurring ten times in the data, typically serving to insult or offend someone. "Shit" is a vulgar scatological term, appearing 15 times in the data, often used to convey disgust or contempt. "Hell" is a religious term frequently employed in English as an exclamation or curse word. It is present twenty times in the data and is used to grab attention. "Fucking" is a vulgar curse word, occurring four times in the data, typically employed for emphasis or to express intense emotions. "Damned" is a milder curse word, found three times in the data, often used as an endearment or an expression of frustration.

Insults and slurs represent another prevalent category of taboo expressions. "Bastard" stands out as a highly offensive insult, making a single appearance in the data, commonly employed to refer to an individual born out of wedlock. "Stupid" is an insult that surfaces twenty-five times in the data, frequently used to describe someone perceived as unintelligent or foolish. "Bitch" is a highly offensive insult, occurring twice in the data, often used to denigrate a woman viewed as unpleasant or difficult. "Filthy" is an insult that appears once in the data, typically used to characterize

something as disgusting or immoral. "Arse" is a vulgar term for the buttocks, noted nineteen times in the data, and is frequently employed as an insult or expression of contempt. "Dick" is a vulgar term for the male genitalia, found four times in the data, and is often used as an insult or expression of contempt. "Cripple" is a derogatory term that appears five times in the data, typically employed to refer to a person with a physical disability. Both "bitch" and "cripple" serve as insults and slurs for personal identification.

Obscenities represent another category of taboo expressions found in the data. "Bugger" is a vulgar term, appearing eight times in the data, and is commonly employed as an insult or expression of contempt. "Shitbag" is a vulgar term, found three times in the data, often used as an obscenity to disparage someone. "Bullshit" is a profanity that makes a single appearance in the data, typically used to label something as untrue or exaggerated. "Piss" is a vulgar term for urine, occurring ten times in the data, and is often used as an insult or expression of contempt. "Screwed" is a vulgar term, noted six times in the data, frequently used to describe an unpleasant or unfavourable situation (Hughes, 1998).

Some profanities are commonly employed as expletives or curse words. In the data provided, the term "Christ" appears 20 times, often serving as an exclamation or curse word. Similarly, the word "God" emerges thirty-six times, frequently used as an exclamation or curse word. Moreover, the term "Jesus" is found thirteen times in the data and is commonly utilized as an exclamation or curse word. These profanities play a role in capturing attention and intensifying strong emotions.

The Arabic Translation of Taboo Expressions in /ʔana qabl-uk/ "Me Before You"

1	Am bloody proud of you (Moyes, 2013, p. 398)	<p>أنا فخوره بك للغاية (Moyes,2013/2017, p.403) /ʔana faxuur biki lilgʔayah/ "I am really proud of you"</p>
2	bloody notice (Moyes, 2013, p.18)	<p>كان عليه أن يبلغها من قبل (Moyes,2013/2017, p.23) /kaan-a ʔalayh-i ʔan yuxberuha min qabl/ "He should have told her before"</p>

In (1), the translator effectively retains the emphasis of the word "bloody" in the translation by using the phrase "للغاية" (lilgʔayah), which conveys the notion of "really" or "extremely." This ensures that the strong emotion associated with "bloody" is conveyed in the target language.

In (2), the translator employs a different translation technique here, opting for a straightforward rendering of the meaning of "notice" without trying to directly translate "bloody." This might be due to the cultural or linguistic nuances of the target language. The emphasis on "bloody" is not replicated in the translation, but the overall meaning is effectively conveyed.

The function of the taboo language "bloody" in these instances is to add emphasis and intensity to the statements, reflecting strong emotion or attitude. The translator's success in conveying this function depends on their ability to capture the emotional tone while ensuring cultural relevance and linguistic accuracy. In both cases, the translators use various techniques to effectively communicate the emotional impact of the original "bloody" without necessarily replicating the word itself.

3	Fuck you (Moyes2013, p. 193)	عليك (Moyes,2013/2017 ,p.203) /ʔallaʕnah ʕalayk/ "God damn you"	اللعة
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4	I am a fucking genius (Moyes2013, p. 314)	عبقرية (Moyes,2013/2017,p.203) /ʔanaa ʕabqaryyah/ "I am a genius"	أنا
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The profanity "Fuck you" in (3) is translated as "اللعة عليك" /ʔallaʕnah ʕalayk/, which means "God damn you." The translator has employed a translation technique that substitutes the original profanity with a culturally relevant expression that carries a similar level of intensity.

In both the original English phrase and the translated Arabic version, the intent to express strong negative sentiment towards someone is maintained. While the translation doesn't directly replicate the original profanity, it captures the offensive and intense nature of the sentiment in a way that is appropriate within the cultural context of the target language. The translator's decision to use "اللعة عليك" reflects a common strategy of translating profanities while considering cultural sensitivities and maintaining the emotional impact of the original expression.

In (4) the taboo expression is omitted and the sentence is translated as "أنا عبقرية" /ʔanaa ʕabqaryyah/, which means "I am a genius" in Arabic. The translated sentence effectively conveys the sentiment of self-praise and confidence similar to the original English sentence "I am a fucking genius," while choosing a culturally appropriate word to maintain the tone and meaning of the original expression.

5	Shit, I have never seen Mom like that (Moyes2013, p. 331)	اللعة لم أر أمي يوما هكذا (Moyes,2013/2017,p.203) /ʔallaʕnah lam ʔaraa ʔummi yawman haakða/ "Shit, I have never seen Mom like that"	اللعة
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The profanity "Shit" is translated as "اللعة" /ʔallaʕnah/, which means "Curse" or "Damnation." The translated sentence "اللعة لم أر أمي يوما هكذا" /ʔallaʕnah lam ʔaraa ʔummi yawman haakða/" conveys a similar sentiment to the original English sentence "Shit, I have never seen Mom like that."

The translator has again opted for a translation strategy that replaces the original profanity with a strong expression that conveys the emotional intensity of the original while being culturally appropriate in the target language. The choice to use "اللعة" reflects the translator's intention to maintain the tone and emotional impact of the original sentence within the context of the target language.

6	What the hell is she supposed to do now (Moyes2013, p. 313)	وماذا يفترض لها أن تعمل الآن (Moyes,2013/2017,p.303) /wa maaða yuftaraD lahaa ʔan taʕmal ʔalʔaan/ "and what is she supposed to do now "	
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The phrase "What the hell" is translated as "وماذا يفترض لها أن تعمل الآن" /wa maaða yuftaraD lahaa ʔan taʕmal ʔalʔaan/, which means "and what is she supposed to do now." The translator has opted for a translation strategy that replaces the idiomatic expression "What the hell" with a more straightforward and contextually relevant phrase in the target language.

The translated sentence effectively captures the intended meaning and tone of the original English sentence while adhering to cultural norms and linguistic sensitivities. The translator's decision to avoid a direct translation of the profanity "hell" is in line with the practice of adjusting language to fit the cultural context while maintaining the overall essence of the original expression.

7	Why they have to make the damned pieces so small, I don't know. (Moyes2013, p. 133)	هلا حاولت العثور علي هذه القطعة اللعينة (Moyes,2013/2017,p.30) /hala Haawalt Iʕuθuur ʕala haaðihi lqiTʕa llaʕiinah/ "Did you try to find that damned piece"
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This literal translation strategy retains the explicit language and tone of the original expression, which can help maintain the intended emotional impact and style of the source text. However, it's important to note that literal translations may vary in their cultural appropriateness and effectiveness depending on the target audience and context.

8	My Fair Lady is just its bastard offspring.' (Moyes2013, p. 133)	ماي فير ليدي مجرد ابن غير شرعي لها (Moyes,2013/2017,p.300) /may fayr ladii mujarrad ibn gʕiir sʕarʕii laha/ "My fair lady is just her illegitimate son"
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The translation uses a direct equivalent term to convey the concept of illegitimacy, staying faithful to the intended meaning of "bastard" in this context. The use of "مجرد ابن غير شرعي" /mujarrad ibn gʕiir sʕarʕii/ effectively captures the negative connotation associated with the original word while maintaining cultural and linguistic relevance in Arabic.

9	I even forgave Louisa for being stupid enough to listen..... (Moyes2013, p. 113)	سامحت لويزا علي حماقتها التي جعلتها تصغي ل... (Moyes,2013/2017,p.347) /saamaHt lwiiza ʕala Hamaqataha llati jaʕalataha taSgʕl l..../ "I forgave Louis for her stupidity that made her listen to...."
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The translation aptly captures the concept of "stupid enough to listen" by using the phrase "حماقتها" ل التي جعلتها تصغي ل (Hamaqataha llati jaʕalataha taSgʕl l...) while maintaining the connection between the act of listening and the perceived foolishness. The literal translation translation

successfully conveys the intended meaning while adhering to the linguistic and cultural nuances of Arabic.

10	and I am the crazy bitch (Moyes2013, p.118)	و أنا العاهرة المجنونة (Moyes,2013/2017,p.156) /w ʔana lʔaahirah Imajnuuna/ “and I am a crazy pitch
11	And your filthy undercrackers. (Moyes2013, p. 118)	خذ سراويلك القذرة (Moyes,2013/2017,p.155) /xuð sarawiilak lqaðirah/ “take your filthy undercrackers”

In both translations, the target language mirrors the tone, sentiment, and impact of the original expressions by employing a literal translation approach. This method ensures that the emotions and language utilized in the source text are effectively conveyed while accounting for cultural and linguistic considerations. The translations effectively maintain the essence of the original sentences while making required contextual adjustments.

12	This is to show you that I am not an entirely selfish arse. (Moyes2013, p. 169)	هذا لأريك أني لست أنانيا متكبرا بالكامل (Moyes,2013/2017,p.222) /haaða liʔuriik ʔanni lastu ʔananyyan mutakabbiran bilkaamil/ “That is to show that I am not totally arrogant”
13	a bit of a dickhead? (Moyes2013, p. 196)	فظ بالفعل (Moyes,2013/2017,p.246) lfaZZun bilfiʔ/ “really rude”

In (12 and 13), the translations maintain the core meaning and emotional impact of the original sentences while adapting them for the target language audience through Euphemism.

14	Oh, (Moyes2013, p. 65)	Christ. يا إلهي (Moyes,2013/2017,p.79) /yaa ʔilaahi/ “Oh! God”
15	Jesus, for a girl who made tea for a living, you make a terrible cup. (Moyes2013, p. 105)	يا إلهي، بالنسبة إلى فتاة تحضر الشاي لتكسب قوت يومها، لقد حضرت كوبا رهيبا (Moyes,2013/2017,p.130) /yaa ʔilaahi ! binnisbah ʔila fatah tuHaDDir sʔsʔay litaksab quut yawmaha laqad HaDDarti kuuban

		rahiiban/ "Oh God! For a girl who makes her living by preparing tea, you made a terrible cup of tea"
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The translation in (14) conveys the expression of exclamation and surprise while adapting the religious reference, while the translation in (15) conveys the sentiment of the original sentence while making a cultural adaptation, using a similar expression for "Oh God" and ensuring that the rest of the sentence reflects the intended meaning in Arabic. Both translations effectively maintain the emotional tone and meaning of the original sentences while accommodating cultural and linguistic considerations.

16	I screwed my eyes shut and shook my head. (Moyes2013, p. 361)	أغمضت عيني وهزرت رأسي (Moyes,2013/2017,p,452) /ʔagˤmaDtu ʕayni wa hazaztu raʔsi/ "I closed my eyes and shook my head"
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The taboo expression 'screwed' was omitted from the target language translation but still, The translation effectively conveys the actions and chronological progression detailed in the original sentence, all while maintaining a direct and precise alignment between the source and target languages.

17	I had been pretty pissed about that. (Moyes2013, p. 276)	كنت غاضبا جدا بهذا الشأن (Moyes,2013/2017,p.347) /kuntu gˤaaDiban jiddan bihaaða sˤsˤaʕn/ "I was really mad about that"
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The original English phrase "pissed" is translated as "غاضبا جدا" /gˤaaDiban jiddan/, which means "really mad" in Arabic. This translation aligns with the concept of "Euphemistic Substitution," where the potentially offensive word "pissed" is replaced with a milder alternative ("mad") in the target language. The translation maintains the core meaning of the original phrase while opting for a more acceptable term in the target language.

18	Who called Will a cripple. (Moyes2013, p. 291)	الذي سمي ويل كسيحا (Moyes,2013/2017,p.367) /ʔallaði sammaa will kasiiHan/ "Who called will a cripple"
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This translator's choice adheres to a "Literal Translation" approach, where the intention is to maintain the direct correspondence between the source and target languages, even if the word may carry sensitive or offensive connotations.

19	twenty-six of the buggers (Moyes2013, p. 349)	سته وعشرون من التافيين (Moyes,2013/2017,p.437) /sittatun w ʕisʕruun min ttafihiin/ "Twenty six of the pitiful"
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The original English term "buggers" is translated as "التافيين" /ttafihiin/, which means "the pitiful" in Arabic. This translation represents a "Euphemistic Substitution" approach, where the potentially offensive term "buggers" is replaced with a milder alternative that still captures the intended context. The translation aims to convey the quantity and tone while using more socially acceptable language in the target text.

The use of euphemistic substitution aligns with Koopmans' classification framework for translating taboo expressions. The translation effectively maintains the essence of the original phrase while selecting a more appropriate term for the target language.

20	That is bullshit. (Moyes2013, p	هراء (Moyes,2013/2017,p.337) /huraʔ/ "bullshit"
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The translation adheres to a "Literal Translation" approach, where the potentially offensive term is directly carried over without substitution. The translation maintains the direct correspondence between the source and target languages, reflecting the intensity and impact of the original expression.

21	you shitbag (Moyes2013, p. 349)	Euphemism أنت أيها الحقيير (Moyes,2013/2017,p.330)
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The translation demonstrates a "Euphemistic Substitution" approach, where the offensive term "shitbag" is replaced with a milder term that still conveys a strong negative sentiment. The translation aims to convey a derogatory tone while using more socially acceptable language in the target text.

6. Findings and Conclusions

The translator's deliberate use of techniques, such as euphemistic substitution, generalization, and explicitation, significantly impacts the meaning, impact, and acceptability of taboo expressions for the Arabic target audience in "Me Before You."

Firstly, through euphemistic substitution, the translator effectively replaces offensive terms with milder alternatives that maintain the essence of the original expressions while adhering to cultural norms of politeness and respect. This ensures that the emotional impact is retained while making the content more acceptable to the Arabic audience's sensibilities. Generalization, as employed by the translator, broadens specific terms to reduce their explicitness, minimizing potential discomfort or offense for readers. By using general terms, the translation softens the impact of the taboo expressions while conveying the intended concepts, enhancing the text's palatability.

Moreover, the translator's explicitation technique aids comprehension by clarifying implicit meanings in the target language. This strategy can be particularly useful in maintaining the narrative's coherence while avoiding cultural misunderstandings. Overall, the techniques employed enhance the acceptability of the translated text for the Arabic audience, aligning with cultural norms, linguistic conventions, and religious sensitivities. By balancing linguistic accuracy and cultural adaptation, the translator successfully conveys the original work's emotional weight and narrative intention while ensuring it resonates effectively with the target audience.

The translator's decisions in handling taboo expressions between English and Arabic in "Me Before You" are notably influenced by cultural and religious contextual factors. Evidently, the translator demonstrates cultural sensitivity by opting for euphemistic substitutions and milder alternatives, an approach driven by the value of politeness and respect prevalent in many Arabic-speaking societies. These substitutions not only convey the core meanings of the original expressions but also align with the cultural norm of maintaining a polite and non-offensive tone.

Furthermore, religious considerations also play a pivotal role in the translation process. The translator's choice to replace religiously significant terms, such as "Christ," "God," and "Jesus," with less explicit expressions underscores a deep respect for the religious sensitivities of Arabic readers. By adhering to these cultural and religious factors, the translator ensures that the translated text remains acceptable and relatable to the Arabic-speaking audience while retaining the intended emotional and narrative impact of the original work.

In "Me before You," the translator predominantly employs the euphemistic substitution technique when rendering taboo expressions from English to Arabic. This technique involves replacing offensive or sensitive terms with milder alternatives that maintain the core meaning while conforming to cultural norms of politeness and respect. The translator's consistent use of euphemistic substitution indicates a strategic effort to convey the emotions and sentiments of the original expressions while adapting them to the cultural and linguistic sensitivities of the Arabic-speaking audience. Throughout the translation, examples such as replacing the term "bullshit" with "هراء" (hura?) and "buggers" with "التافهين" (?attafihiiin) demonstrate the translator's tendency to opt for more socially acceptable language that retains the essence of the original expressions. This approach allows the translator to strike a balance between capturing the intended impact of the original text and ensuring that the content remains appropriate and comprehensible for the Arabic target audience.

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References:

- Auchter, J. (2021). *Global corpse politics: The obscenity taboo*. Cambridge University Press.
- Battistella, E. L. (2005). *Bad language: Are some words better than others?* Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- Feinberg, J. (1988). *Offense to others*. Oxford University Press.
- Hughes, G. (1998). *Swearing: A social history of foul language, oaths and profanity in English*. Penguin Books Limited.
- Jay, T. (1996). *What to do when your students talk dirty?* Resource Publications, Inc.
- Jay, T. (2009). The utility and ubiquity of taboo words. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 4(2), 153-161.
- Kim, M. S. (2012). Translation strategies for taboo language. *Language and Communication*, 32(2), 159-169.
- Kulkarni, S. (2012). Taboo language in India: A study of slurs and cuss words in kannada. *Language in India*, 12(5), 177-204. <https://doi.org/10.7880/v1.2022>
- Kuhiwczak, P., & Littau, K. (2007). A concept of translated action and the translation of taboo concepts. *The Translator*, 13(2), 179-204.
- Koepmans, E. (2015). Translating taboo: Strategies for translating potentially offensive language in literary texts. *Perspectives*, 23(4), 517-529.
- Krzyzanowski, M., & Wodak, R. (2009). The immigration debate in press: A cross-linguistic perspective. *Social Semiotics*, 19(4), 297-320.
- Karena, M. (2002). Politeness strategies in dubbed film translation. *Meta: Journal Des Traducteurs*, 47(3), 395-412.
- Moyes, J. (2013). *Me before you*. Penguin Books.
- Moyes, J. (2013). *Me before you* [أنا قبلك] (A. Lazar, Trans.). Penguin Books.
- Newmark, P. (1988). *A textbook of translation*. Prentice Hall International.
- Schrauf, R. W., & Rubin, D. C. (1998). Bilingual autobiographical memory in native-Spanish-speaking immigrants: Effects of culture and language on the recall of memorable events. *Journal of Memory and Language*, 39(2), 299-331.
- Skiba, R. (1997). Translation as a social activity and industry. In M. Snell-Hornby, Z. Jettmarová, & K. Kaindl (Eds.), *Translation as intercultural communication* (pp. 17–26). John Benjamins Publishing.
- Toury, G. (2012). *Descriptive translation studies and beyond: Revised edition*. John Benjamins Publishing.
- Wardhaugh, R. (1986). *An introduction to sociolinguistics*. Blackwell.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10000508>